

Two Spanish inventions in the XV – century

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Member of the Asociación Internacional de Hispanistas

The unknown Lucena is Francesch Vicent

The first printed chess book in the world was written by Francesch Vicent¹. About two years later appeared the second printed chess book in the world by Lucena², son of Juan Ramírez de Lucena, and ambassador of the Catholic Monarchs. The latest book of Lucena was bound with the work *Repetición de amores*. Around this time Lucena wrote another work³ that has been lost. We have explained the various chess manuscripts and books of Lucena and Francesch Vicent In a previous study⁴. The aim of this study is to identify the real name of Lucena.

Thanks to the position of his father Juan Ramirez de Lucena, Lucena was able to have contact at the highest level with the nobility in Italy. Already early in the nineties Lucena had the necessary contacts with the printing houses to promote certain books. He was active as translator of Latin and Italian texts. He probably worked for some time with the famous Nebrija who had a printing house in Salamanca, or he had some form of contact with Nebrija. It appears that we do not see the term “dama” (lady) of chess in the dictionary of 1492, though 3 years later we observe Lucena’s activity in the Latin dictionary.

Nebrija⁵ had already introduced new words such as "dama (lady) is almost lady" (Domina-ae - novum) and "andarraia" (calcolorum ludus - novum) in his Latin dictionary of 1495. Novum occurs here in the sense of something new. Nebrija created

¹ **VICENT, Francesch** (1495) Libre dels joch partitis del Scachs en nombre de 100 ordenat e compost per mi Francesch Vicent, nat en la ciutat de Segorbe, criat e vehí de la insigne e valeroso ciutat de Valencia. Y acaba: A loor e gloria de nostre Redemtor Jesu Christ fou acabat lo dit libre dels jochs partitis dels scachs en la sinsigne ciutat de Valencia e estamat per mans de Lope de Roca Alemany e Pere Trinchet librere á XV días de Maig del any MCCCCLXXXV

² **LUCENA** (1497) Repetición de amores e arte de Axedres con CL Juegos de Partido. Salamanca

³ **LUCENA** (1497?) Tractado sobre la muerte de don Diego de Azevedo, compuesto por Lucena

⁴ **WESTERVELD, Govert** (2016) *Why Francesch Vicent Did n\Not Like to Use His Name*. Academia de Estudios Humanísticos de Blanca, N° 3, pp. 1-9. Doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.26530.22727 (Researchgate.net)

⁵ This author wrote a Spanish-Latin dictionary that was published around 1493 - 1495. We tried to find the same words in the Latin dictionary Hispanum from 1492, but these terms do not exist there.

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this dictionary between 1492 and 1495 and it becomes clear that the addition of these new words in this dictionary was before the edition of the first chess book of Francesch Vicent in Valencia. According to Nebrija Spain⁶ had to teach the world its culture. Lucena could do that in Salamanca, because he was aware of the earlier chess activities in Valencia and those of his father Juan Ramirez de Lucena. The printing climate was now appropriate, with intellectuals like Nebrija in his favour, to have a work in the Castilian language as soon as possible. Then Spain might spread the work to Castile and other places of the world, one more way of demonstrating its power.

Lucena completely disappeared from the scene in 1497 and we find his name only abroad again in three foreign chess manuscripts, one from around 1505, another one from around 1515 and the other from around 1530 where anonymous writers mention the name of Lucena. Apparently Lucena does not use his name “Lucena” anymore after 1497.

The Inquisition

Around the year 1503 the chief inquisitor of Zaragoza Hernando de Montemayor prosecuted Carlos Ramírez de Lucena, the brother of his father, and his other relatives on suspicion of Judaism. Juan Ramírez de Lucena wrote a letter to the king⁷ complaining that the judge did not consider the exemption, and requested letters to the royal ambassador in Rome and the pope to "whatever be just, provide me and my brother with." He had reasons to feel uneasy about him and his brother Fernando de Lucena who was also a protonotary as we have seen in other documents, because another protonotary, Felipe Clemente⁸, was also arrested by the Inquisition and sentenced in Seo of Zaragoza on July 30 1503.

The text of this letter to the king is important in the bibliography of Juan Ramirez de Lucena and Jeronimo Miguel Briongos observed in his doctoral thesis⁹ that the text was not written by Juan Ramirez de Lucena. This is correct and the JGAAP program showed

⁶ To facilitate the reading we say Spain. It's evident that the Catholic monarchs never used the form "Kings of Spain" in their titles, but they always used *"King and Queen of Castile, of León, of Aragon, of Siçilia, of Toledo ..."*

⁷ **WESTERVELD, Govert** (2015). The Ambassador Juan Ramírez de Lucena, the father of the chessbook writer Lucena. Academia de Estudios Humanísticos en Blanca, pp.132-134.

⁸ **COMBESCURE THIRY, Monique** (2003). El libro verde de Aragón. Introducción y transcripción Monique Combescure Thiry Presentación y estudio preliminar Miguel Ángel Motis Dolader. Zaragoza, pp. 92-93

⁹ **MIGUEL BRIONGOS, Jerónimo** (2012) De Vita Felici o Diálogo sobre la Vida Feliz, de Juan de Lucena: Edición crítica. Tesis doctoral, Volume I, Departamento de Filología Española. Universidad autónoma de Barcelona, pp. CVII – CX

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that the text was written by his son Lucena. We have explained the characteristics and way of using of JGAAP¹⁰ in an article about *Lazarillo*. We used the following possible authors in this program for detecting the authorship of the letter that was addressed to king Ferdinand:

Alonso de Cardona (*Question de amor*)

Alonso de Proaza (*Some texts of his*)

Diego de San Pedro (*Arnalte y Lucenda; Cárcel de amor*)

Fernando de Rojas (*some texts from his testament in 1541*)

Francisco López de Villalobos (*Costumbres humanas*)

Hernando del Castillo (*Cancionero*)

Juan Ramirez de Lucena (*Vita Beata and other works*)

Juan de Flores (*Grimalte and Grisel*)

Juan del Encina (*Complete works*)

Lucena (chess book, *Arte de Ajedrez*, 1497; different parts of *Repeticion de amores*)

ramirezlucena1503.txt D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\ramirezlucena1503.txt

Canonicizers:

Normalize Whitespace

EventDrivers:

Character NGrams n : 2

EventCullers:

Most Common Events numevents : 50

Analysis:

Nearest Neighbor Driver with metric Cosine Distance

1. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\lucenaintroduccionajedrez.txt 0.018239974446037865
2. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\repeticionamores.txt 0.02420731818776345
3. Diego de San Pedro -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\arnalte obra completa.txt 0.025050064102323022
4. Diego de San Pedro -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\carceldeamor.txt 0.025103775927774574
5. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Lucena pp 15-37.txt 0.025716406646892787
6. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\repamores cartas principio lucena.txt 0.026677006730223662
7. Alonso de Cardona -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\alonsodecardona lleva todo.txt 0.027491755134194773
8. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Lucena pp37-59.txt 0.027981218337152725
9. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\repamorespreambulo.txt 0.02900994184196204
10. Francisco de Villaloba -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\vallalobosglosa.txt 0.029298462833010963
11. Diego de San Pedro -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\carcel amor prologo.txt 0.03241808315110284
12. Juan del Encina -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\encina al principe.txt 0.03313405534626768
13. Diego de San Pedro -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\arnalte prologo.txt 0.036046088950876576
14. Francisco de Villaloba -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\vallaloba costumbres humanas.txt 0.03667238965867525
15. Juan de Flores -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\griselobra.txt 0.03737601572314975

¹⁰ WESTERVELD, Govert (2016,) Lazarillo de Tormes and La Celestina. Why Jordi Bilbeny Is Right. Academia de Estudios Humanísticos de Blanca, N°. 4, pp. 1-7. Doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31720.67848 (Researchgate.net)

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16. Juan del Encina -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\encina completo.txt 0.03856314741106193
17. Alonso de Proaza -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\proaza Toledo1500.txt 0.04008268899104406
18. Juan del Encina -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\encina eglogas antes 1509.txt 0.04068080213822112
19. Juan de Flores -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\grimalteobra.txt 0.040926751913926585
20. Fernando de Rojas -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\fernando de rojas3.txt 0.04347985263581189
21. Alonso de Proaza -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\proaza Valencia1514.txt 0.04438736970812329
22. Alonso de Proaza -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\alonsodeproaza4.txt 0.044470495320933945
23. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Lucena pp59-66.txt 0.04606399992363264
24. Fernando de Rojas -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\fernando de rojas1 testamento notario.txt 0.04648699748431884
25. Juan del Encina -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\encina1521.txt 0.047024482013468316
26. Alonso de Proaza -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\proaza acrostico.txt 0.04738513573158121
27. Juan del Encina -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\encinacoplas 1521.txt 0.047943996505402486
28. Francisco de Villaloba -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\ villaloboscarts.txt 0.049897861952820755
29. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\vitabeata prologo.txt 0.05341805412348366
30. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\lucena preambulo.txt 0.05505473370236036
31. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\vita beata.txt 0.05943343812802959
32. Fernando de Rojas -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\fernando de rojas test2.txt 0.06603584120257666
33. Hernando del Castillo -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\hernando de castillo prologo.txt 0.06872122316860219
34. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Ramirez Lucena a Jorge Manrique.txt 0.069259203521019
35. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Ramirez Lucena exhortatoria.txt 0.07118903780520658
36. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\RamirezLucena a Zapata.txt 0.07120132426723214
37. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\ramirezlucena sermon.txt 0.0885694221456883
38. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\lucenalibrocarto.txt 0.089242360212753
39. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\RamirezLucena a galardones.txt 0.10697174064090265
40. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Lucena poema pp69-70.txt 0.11520107188483919
41. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\repamorespreambuloajedrez.txt 0.12442354586236559

Furthermore Ricardo Calvo¹¹ thought that Calisto was *the* literary reincarnation of Lucena¹² in *La Celestina*.

Something that could not obtain the approval of another Spanish chess historian, Pérez de Arriaga¹³, and María Luisa Gómez-Ivanov considers it a speculation of little reliability¹⁴. Calvo was one of the first researchers¹⁵ after Rubio¹⁶ who detected that

¹¹ **CALVO, Ricardo** (1997) Lucena. La evasión en ajedrez del converso Calisto. Ciudad Real: Perea Ediciones. Págs 55

¹² **CALVO, Ricardo** (1997) Lucena. La evasión en ajedrez del converso Calisto. Ciudad Real: Perea Ediciones, p. 55

¹³ **PÉREZ DE ARRIAGA, Joaquín** (1997) *Lucena. El incunable de Lucena*: Primer arte de ajedrez moderno. Madrid: Polifemo, p. 26

¹⁴ **GÓMEZ-IVANOV, María Luisa** (2005) *Algunas noticias sobre Lucena, hijo de Juan Ramírez de Lucena y autor de Repetición de amores e arte de axedrez: con CL juegos de partido* (Salamanca, h. 1497). In eHumanista, Volume 5, pp. 96-112

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there was a relationship between *Repetición de amores* and *La Celestina*. Today we know that Calvo's idea was visionary.

The text of the monologue of Calisto in *La Celestina* of which we have made an analysis was the following:

¡Oh mezquino yo!, cuánto me es agradable de mi natural la solicitud y silencio y oscuridad. No sé si lo causa que me vino a la memoria la traición que hice en partir de aquella señora, que tanto amo, hasta que más fuera de día, o el dolor de mi deshonra. ¡Ay, ay!, que esto es. Esta herida es la que siento ahora, que se ha resfriado. Ahora que está helada la sangre, que ayer hervía; ahora que veo la mengua de mi casa, la falta de mi servicio, la perdición de mi patrimonio, la infamia que tiene mi persona de la muerte, que de mis criados se ha seguido. ¿Qué hice? ¿En qué me detuve? ¿Cómo me puedo sufrir, que no me mostré luego presente, como hombre injuriado, vengador, soberbio y acelerado de la manifiesta injusticia que me fue hecha?

¡Oh mísera suavidad de esta brevísima vida! ¿Quién es de ti tan codicioso que no quiera más morir luego que gozar un año de vida denostado y prorrogarle con deshonra, corrompiendo la buena fama de los pasados? Mayormente que no hay hora cierta ni limitada ni a un solo momento. Deudores somos sin tiempo, continuo estamos obligados a pagar luego. ¿Por qué no salí a inquirir siquiera la verdad de la secreta causa de mi manifiesta perdición? ¡Oh breve deleite mundano! ¡Cómo duran poco y cuestan mucho tus dulzores! No se compra tan caro el arrepentir.

¡Oh triste yo! ¿Cuándo se restaurará tan grande pérdida? ¿Qué haré? ¿Qué consejo tomaré? ¿A quién descubriré mi mengua? ¿Por qué lo celo a los otros mis servidores y parientes? Trasquilánme en concejo y no lo saben en mi casa. Salir quiero; pero, si salgo para decir que he estado presente, es tarde; si ausente, es temprano. Y para proveer amigos y criados antiguos, parientes y allegados, es menester tiempo, y para buscar armas y otros aparejos de venganza. ¡Oh cruel juez!, ¡y qué mal pago me has dado del pan que de mi padre comiste! Yo pensaba que pudiera con tu favor matar mil hombres sin temor de castigo, inicuo falsario, perseguidor de verdad, hombre de bajo suelo. Bien dirán de ti que te hizo alcalde mengua de hombres buenos.

Miraras que tú y los que mataste en servir a mis pasados y a mí érades compañeros; mas, cuando el vil está rico, no tiene pariente ni amigo. ¿Quién pensara que tú me habías de destruir? No hay, cierto, cosa más empecible que el incogitado enemigo. ¿Por qué quisiste que dijese: del monte sale con que se arde y que crié cuervo que me sacase el ojo? Tú eres público delincuente y mataste a los que son privados. Y pues sabe que menor delito es el privado que el público, menor su utilidad, según las leyes de Atenas disponen. Las cuales no son escritas con sangre; antes muestran que es menor yerro no condenar los malhechores, que punir los inocentes. ¡Oh cuán peligroso es seguir justa causa delante de injusto juez!

Loose translation:

¹⁵ CARBALLO PICAZO, Antonio (1956) *Res. De Repetición de amores*, ed. Jacob Ornstein. Revista de Filología Española, N° 40, (Pp. 299 – 303), Citation on p. 302. Cited by CALVO, Ricardo (1997) *Lucena. La evasión en ajedrez del converso Calisto*. Perea Ediciones. Pedro Muñoz (Ciudad Real), p. 19

¹⁶ RUBIO GARCÍA, Luis (1985) *Estudios sobre La Celestina*. Universidad de Murcia, Departamento de Filología Románica

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O wretch that I am, how suitable and natural unto me is solitariness, silence, and darkness. I know not whether the cause of it be, that there cometh now to mind the treason that I have committed in taking my leave of that lady, whom I so dearly love, before it was further day ? Or whether it be the grief, which I conceive of my dishonour by the death of my servants? Ay, ay, this is it that grieves me, this is that wound whereof I bleed. Now that I am grown a little cooler; now that that blood waxeth cold, which yesterday did boil in me; now that I see the decaying of my house, my want of service, the wasting of my patrimony, and the infamy which lights upon me by the death of my servants——what have I done ! ¿ How can I possibly contain myself ? How can I forbear any longer, but that I should presently express myself as a man much wronged, and show myself a proud and speedy revenger of that open injury which hath been offered me? Oh! the miserable sweetness of this most short and transitory life! Who is he so covetous of thy countenance, who will not rather choose to die presently than to enjoy a whole year of a shameful life, and to prorogue it with dishonour, losing the good report and honourable memory of his noble ancestors? Especially, sithence that in this world we have not any certain or limited time, no, not so much as a moment or a minute. We are debtors without time: we stand continually bound to present payment. Why have I not gone abroad, and made all the inquiry I can after the secret cause of my open perdition? O thou short delight of the world, how little do thy pleasure[s] last! And how much do they cost! Repentance should not be bought so dear. O miserable that I am, when shall I recover so great a loss ? What shall I do ? What counsel shall I take? To whom shall I discover my disgrace? Why do I conceal it from the rest of my servants and kinsfolk? They clip and note my good name in their council-house and public assembly, and make me infamous throughout the whole kingdom: and they of mine own house and kindred must not know of it. I will out amongst them: but if I go out and tell them that I was present, it is too late; if absent, it is too soon. And to provide me of friends, ancient servants, and near allies, it will ask some time, as likewise that we be furnished with arms, and other preparations of vengeance. O thou cruel judge, what ill payment hast thou made me of that my father's bread, which so often thou hast eaten! I thought that by thy favour I might have killed a thousand men without controlment. O thou falsifier of faith, thou persecutor of the truth, thou man moulded of the baser sort of earth! Truly is the proverb verified in thee, that for want of good men thou wast made a judge. Thou shouldst have considered, that thyself and those thou didst put to death were servants to my ancestors and me, and thy fellows and companions. But when the base to riches doth ascend, he regardeth neither kindred nor friend. Who Would have thought that thou wouldst have wrought my undoing? But there is nothing more hurt-ful than an unexpected enemy. Why wouldst thou that it should be verified of thee, that that which came out of Etna, should consume Etna, and that I hatched the crow, which picked out mine eyes? Thou thyself art a public delinquent, and yet punishest those that were private offenders. But I would have thee to know, that a private fault is less than a public, and less the inconvenience and danger; at least, according to the laws of Athens, which were not written in blood, but do show that it is a less error not to condemn a delinquent than to punish the innocent. O how hard a matter is it, to follow a just cause before an unjust judge!

The writing style of this part of the monologue of Calisto in Chapter XIV of *La Celestina* corresponds to Lucena according to the JGAAP program:

celestina monologo calisto.txt D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\celestina monologo calisto.txt

Canonicizers:

Normalize Whitespace

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EventDrivers:

Character NGrams n : 2

EventCullers:

Most Common Events numevents : 50

Analysis:

Nearest Neighbor Driver with metric Cosine Distance

1. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\repamores cartas principio lucena.txt 0.0173554190061449
2. Diego de San Pedro -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\arnalte obra completa.txt 0.0174261768806957
3. Diego de San Pedro -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\carceldeamor.txt 0.021646823424778527
4. Diego de San Pedro -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\arnalte prologo.txt 0.023685544692094274
5. Juan de Flores -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\griselobra.txt 0.025402863443752866
6. Alonso de Cardona -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\alonsodecardona lleva todo.txt 0.025755420307049026
7. Juan de Flores -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\grimalteobra.txt 0.026950532227737356
8. Juan del Encina -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\encina eglogas antes 1509.txt 0.02860404144396045
9. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Lucena pp37-59.txt 0.030030671740488457
10. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\lucenaintroduccionajedrez.txt 0.030299828074540236
11. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\repeticionamores.txt 0.030483423620106587
12. Francisco de Villaloba -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\villaloba costumbres humanas.txt 0.03540692685831015
13. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Lucena pp 15-37.txt 0.03553775995809105
14. Diego de San Pedro -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\carcel amor prologo.txt 0.03612522296559817
15. Juan del Encina -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\encina al principe.txt 0.036857284679693514
16. Francisco de Villaloba -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\villalobosglosa.txt 0.03758767188363299
17. Juan del Encina -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\encina completo.txt 0.0397378079053482
18. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\repamorespreambulo.txt 0.0397872155526261
19. Juan del Encina -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\encina1521.txt 0.04125882050616936
20. Juan del Encina -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\encinacoplas 1521.txt 0.04295991974130131
21. Alonso de Proaza -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\alonsodeproaza4.txt 0.04441668774535534
22. Alonso de Proaza -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\proaza Toledo1500.txt 0.044593126857002896
23. Alonso de Proaza -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\proaza acrostico.txt 0.0450370749704222
24. Fernando de Rojas -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\fernando de rojas3.txt 0.046108604327132485
25. Fernando de Rojas -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\fernando de rojas1 testamento notario.txt 0.046612110636522375
26. Alonso de Proaza -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\proaza Valencia1514.txt 0.04688069260149497
27. Francisco de Villaloba -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\villaloboscarteras.txt 0.047261157498718065
28. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\vitabeata prologo.txt 0.049459398686485745
29. Hernando del Castillo -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\hernando de castillo prologo.txt 0.05506287916495445
30. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\vita beata.txt 0.05670663392624886
31. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Lucena pp59-66.txt 0.058112928110156004
32. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\lucena preambulo.txt 0.06283391777152103
33. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Ramirez Lucena a Jorge Manrique.txt 0.06837536617570528
34. Fernando de Rojas -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\fernando de rojas test2.txt 0.06937399712946335
35. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\RamirezLucena a Zapata.txt 0.06956440667945174
36. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Ramirez Lucena exhortatoria.txt 0.06956606284561195
37. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\ramirezlucena sermon.txt 0.08100898955475189
38. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\RamirezLucena a galardones.txt 0.09928306198156556
39. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\lucenalibrocarta.txt 0.10087716145498471
40. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Lucena poema pp69-70.txt 0.1117032857639022
41. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\repamorespreambuloajedrez.txt 0.1275918959438529

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The situation of Francesch Vicent is not much better than that of Lucena. After publishing his chess book in 1495 we can only trace him twice. The first time was in 1500 when Francesch Vicent had the important position of Justice in Segorbe¹⁷, his hometown.

In 1998 Rafael Martín, chronicler of Segorbe, found a document linked to Francesch Vicent and Segorbe in 1500¹⁸. We analyzed this small document, which holds texts of the earlier mentioned author, with the JGAAP program. The result of the analysis is as follows:

franceschvicent2.txt D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\franceschvicent2.txt

Canonicizers:

Normalize Whitespace

EventDrivers:

Character NGrams n : 2

EventCullers:

Most Common Events numevents : 50

Analysis:

Nearest Neighbor Driver with metric Cosine Distance

1. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\lucenaintroduccionajedrez.txt 0.08226918236368119
2. Diego de San Pedro -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\carceldeamor.txt 0.08262068444147408
3. Alonso de Cardona -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\alonsodecardona lleva todo.txt 0.08290393985479161
4. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Lucena pp 15-37.txt 0.08556138308706485
5. Alonso de Proaza -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\alonsodeproaza4.txt 0.0862694046945659
6. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Lucena pp59-66.txt 0.0879761320134902
7. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\repeticionamores.txt 0.08840436886672387
8. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\repamorespreambulo.txt 0.08841920526174718
9. Juan de Flores -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\grimalteobra.txt 0.08887432290279218
10. Diego de San Pedro -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\arnalte obra completa.txt 0.08974167931723331
11. Fernando de Rojas -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\fernando de rojas1 testamento notario.txt 0.09286711257489377
12. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\celestina monologos calisto.txt 0.09380653200295963
13. Fernando de Rojas -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\fernando de rojas3.txt 0.09457412800070375
14. Juan de Flores -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\griselobra.txt 0.09508088976375972
15. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\ramirezlucena1503.txt 0.09532342453376141
16. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\repamores cartas principio lucena.txt 0.09733095456013263
17. Francisco de Villaloba -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\villaloba costumbres humanas.txt 0.09747490502888223

¹⁷ **GARZÓN ROGER, José Antonio** (2005) *The Return of Franchesch Vicent*. The History of the Birth and Expansion of Modern Chess, pp. 436-437

¹⁸ **GARZÓN ROGER, José Antonio** (2005) *The Return of Franchesch Vicent*. The History of the Birth and Expansion of Modern Chess, pp. 436-437

Two Spanish inventions in the XV – century

SALES:

<http://www.lulu.com/spotlight/moriscoricote>

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18. Juan del Encina -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\encina al principe.txt 0.10127377709838292
19. Juan del Encina -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\encina completo.txt 0.10144878703382121
20. Francisco de Villaloba -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\vallaloboscarts.txt 0.10325097586500553
21. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Lucena pp37-59.txt 0.10478368487393086
22. Francisco de Villaloba -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\vallalobosglosa.txt 0.10735650955454912
23. Alonso de Proaza -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\proaza Valencia1514.txt 0.10744214134907315
24. Alonso de Proaza -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\proaza Toledo1500.txt 0.11008339504708764
25. Alonso de Proaza -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\proaza acrostico.txt 0.11084760281954109
26. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\vitabeata prologo.txt 0.11142413572945498
27. Juan del Encina -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\encinacoplas1521.txt 0.1131025382140185
28. Juan del Encina -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\encina1521.txt 0.11349423763654509
29. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Ramirez Lucena a Jorge Manrique.txt 0.11425427855487447
30. Juan del Encina -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\encina eglogas antes 1509.txt 0.11507566962588356
31. Hernando del Castillo -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\hernando de castillo prologo.txt 0.11658010441288646
32. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\repamorespreambuloajedrez.txt 0.12314412013922527
33. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\lucena preambulo.txt 0.12330897435362176
34. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\ramirezlucena sermon.txt 0.12547659020897228
35. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\vita beata.txt 0.1272441763173907
36. Fernando de Rojas -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\fernando de rojas test2.txt 0.12795631045281963
37. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\RamirezLucena a galardones.txt 0.13736985263606616
38. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Ramirez Lucena exhortatoria.txt 0.14189701915784936
39. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\RamirezLucena a Zapata.txt 0.14207899137434588
40. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\lucenalibrocoarto.txt 0.1527191717716816
41. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Lucena poema pp69-70.txt 0.17863965055468478

The second time was when the chess historian Alessandro Sanvito¹⁹ discovered that a certain Spaniard by the name of Francesco served as chessmaster of Lucrezia Borgia in 1506. Chess historians agree that this can only have been Francesch Vicent, but it is clear that after 1501 Francesch Vicent does not use his complete name elsewhere.

However, writers cannot suddenly disappear, because they like writing and so we have to trace the whereabouts of Lucena and Francesch Vicent, probably under other names and activities. Chess historians studied various chess manuscripts in Italy. Their findings clearly show that Francesch Vicent continued to be active not only in Ferrara, but also in Cesena, Perugia, and Rome.

1502-1512 MS Cesena

The manuscript of Cesena of 356 pages has a lot of similarities with the Perugia Manuscript. The Codex in the register of the library is recorded as Ludi varii, idest

¹⁹ SANVITO, Alessandro (1999) Il maestro di scacchi spagnola di Lucezia Borgia. In: L'Italia Scacchistica, issue 1131, December 1999, pp. 392 and 393

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Ludus rebellionis. Ludus subtilitatis primorum. Partiti de 2 tracti. Ludus ad capiendum ovines. The content of Francesch Vicent's chess book in the MS. 166.74 of the Malatestiana Library of Cesena was studied by José Antonio Garzón Roger²⁰.

There was very little text available from the manuscript for making an analysis by JGAAP. Nevertheless, JGAAP showed that the Aragonese Francesc Vicent is nobody else but our Lucena, son of Juan Ramírez de Lucena.

vicent2015 Cesena.txt D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\vicent2015 Cesena.txt

Canoniziers:

Normalize Whitespace

EventDrivers:

Character NGrams n : 2

EventCullers:

Most Common Events numevents : 50

Analysis:

Nearest Neighbor Driver with metric Cosine Distance

1. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\ramirezlucena1503.txt 0.11723701596182323
2. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\lucenaintroduccionajedrez.txt 0.11765735701184776
3. Fernando de Rojas -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\fernando de rojas test2.txt 0.12692914686660495
4. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\repamores cartas principio lucena.txt 0.13349804210785698
5. Alonso de Cardona -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\alonsodecardona lleva todo.txt 0.13727278079131455
6. Diego de San Pedro -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\carceldeamor.txt 0.1397824127381092
7. Juan de Flores -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\grimalteobra.txt 0.14208801635179902
8. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\repeticionamores.txt 0.15068612195297137
9. Francisco de Villaloba -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\villalobosglosa.txt 0.15199126536838337
10. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Lucena pp37-59.txt 0.1523538253604284
11. Diego de San Pedro -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\arnalte obra completa.txt 0.15351773191018891
12. Juan del Encina -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\encina al principe.txt 0.15481189191495992
13. Fernando de Rojas -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\fernando de rojas3.txt 0.15517509762010118
14. Juan de Flores -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\griselobra.txt 0.15686551999378695
15. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\repamorespreambulo.txt 0.15712210111101854
16. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Lucena pp 15-37.txt 0.15821295097186716
17. Francisco de Villaloba -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\villaloba costumbres humanas.txt 0.15828182574356997
18. Fernando de Rojas -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\fernando de rojas1 testamento notario.txt 0.1594675888554643
19. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Lucena pp59-66.txt 0.16309347854299772
20. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\celestina monologos calisto.txt 0.1639560999078693
21. Juan del Encina -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\encina completo.txt 0.1639622556657664
22. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\vitabeata prologo.txt 0.16416832955148675
23. Juan del Encina -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\encina eglogas antes 1509.txt 0.16693066485392405
24. Francisco de Villaloba -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\villaloboscintas.txt 0.17361872365268027
25. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\lucena preambulo.txt 0.1787346146366945
26. Alonso de Proaza -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\proaza Toledo1500.txt 0.17952455183261506

²⁰ **GARZÓN ROGER, José Antonio** (2005) *The Return of Francesch Vicent*. The History of the Birth and Expansion of Modern Chess. (Foreword Anatoli Karpov). Generalitat Valenciana, Conselleria de Cultura, Educació i Esport: Fundació Jaume II el Just, Valencia, pp. 398 and 440

Two Spanish inventions in the XV – century

SALES:

<http://www.lulu.com/spotlight/moriscoricote>

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27. Alonso de Proaza -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\alonsodeproaza4.txt 0.18053580405303127
28. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\lucenalibrocoarto.txt 0.18057966704489736
29. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\vita beata.txt 0.18183579871303468
30. Juan del Encina -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\encina1521.txt 0.1852239855311092
31. Juan del Encina -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\encinacoplas1521.txt 0.1863254312080792
32. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Lucena poema pp69-70.txt 0.18817312669659025
33. Alonso de Proaza -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\proaza Valencia1514.txt 0.18964671817112566
34. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Ramirez Lucena exhortatoria.txt 0.18987922741926377
35. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\RamirezLucena a Zapata.txt 0.19015637106675454
36. Hernando del Castillo -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\hernando de castillo prologo.txt 0.19020203240742417
37. Alonso de Proaza -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\proaza acrostico.txt 0.19923021957904063
38. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Ramirez Lucena a Jorge Manrique.txt 0.21363396603004547
39. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\ramirezlucena sermon.txt 0.21749917163349242
40. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\RamirezLucena a galardones.txt 0.2387381350597133
41. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\repamorespreambuloajedrez.txt 0.27991602630963097

1502-1506 MS Perugia

Another anonymous chess manuscript is the one from Perugia. Today this manuscript of 196 pages is preserved in the Augusta Library of Perugia²¹ under the signature MS 775 (L.27). José Antonio Garzón Roger²² studied this manuscript that is not complete and that had to do with chess work of Francesch Vicent.

1511 Giovanni Chachi's chess manuscript

The Dominican Library „Regia Biblioteca Casanatense” in Rome houses an Italian chess manuscript (Cod. E. VI. 3. 4º) of Joannes Chachi from 1511. Apparently he came from Terni in Umbria²³.

1512 The chess book of Damiano

The chess book of Damiano was printed in Rome in 1512 by Stephen Guillireti and Herenles Nani. The work by means of a foreword was dedicated to Sr. Joangeorgio

²¹ SANVITO, Alessandro (2002) Das Rätsel des Kelten-Spiels. In: Board Game Studies, Number 5, pp. 9-24. Citation on p. 19

²² GARZÓN ROGER, José Antonio (2005) *The Return of Francesch Vicent*. The History of the Birth and Expansion of Modern Chess. (Foreword Anatoli Karpov). Generalitat Valenciana, Conselleria de Cultura, Educació i Esport: Fundació Jaume II el Just, Valencia, p. 398

²³ MURRAY, Harold J.R. (1913). A History of Chess, pp. 727-733.

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SALES:

<http://www.lulu.com/spotlight/moriscoricote>

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Caesarino Romano. The foreword and texts of the book of Damiano were written by Lucena according to JGAAP²⁴.

damianoforeword1.txt D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\damianoforeword1.txt

Canonizers:

Normalize Whitespace

EventDrivers:

Character NGrams n : 2

EventCullers:

Most Common Events numevents : 50

Analysis:

Nearest Neighbor Driver with metric Cosine Distance

1. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\ramirezlucena1503.txt 0.0968743414097899
2. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\repamores cartas principio lucena.txt 0.10183801264860648
3. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\lucenaintroduccionajedrez.txt 0.11894348904134322
4. Alonso de Cardona -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\alonsodecardona lleva todo.txt 0.12194120458516378
5. Diego de San Pedro -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\carceldeamor.txt 0.12611516436830372
6. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\celestina monologos calisto.txt 0.12981977059120287
7. Diego de San Pedro -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\arnalte obra completa.txt 0.13301953343831852
8. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\lucena preambulo.txt 0.13808856773554667
9. Fernando de Rojas -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\fernando de rojas3.txt 0.14123036489539043
10. Fernando de Rojas -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\fernando de rojas test2.txt 0.14565276288448925
11. Francisco de Villaloba -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\vallalobosglosa.txt 0.1471869434535532
12. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\repeticionamores.txt 0.1476961495035708
13. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\repamorespreambulo.txt 0.14850841640107193
14. Fernando de Rojas -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\fernando de rojas1 testamento notario.txt 0.14890051692062534
15. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\vitabeata prologo.txt 0.14914845191238768
16. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Lucena pp 15-37.txt 0.15080501292713921
17. Juan de Flores -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\grimalteobra.txt 0.15370693407604163
18. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Lucena pp37-59.txt 0.15634704496325713
19. Alonso de Proaza -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\proaza Toledo1500.txt 0.15805581691856208
20. Alonso de Proaza -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\proaza acrostico.txt 0.16071382920858834
21. Juan del Encina -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\encina1521.txt 0.16107207630015696
22. Alonso de Proaza -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\alonsodeproaza4.txt 0.16120280812220078
23. Francisco de Villaloba -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\vallaloboscintas.txt 0.16159369606554508
24. Juan del Encina -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\encina al principe.txt 0.1621614013510284
25. Juan del Encina -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\encinacoplas1521.txt 0.16296740689316447
26. Alonso de Proaza -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\proaza Valencia1514.txt 0.16772889296889282
27. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Lucena pp59-66.txt 0.16844974654187428
28. Juan del Encina -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\encina eglogas antes 1509.txt 0.16890466072616106
29. Juan de Flores -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\griselobra.txt 0.16911109256165036
30. Francisco de Villaloba -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\vallaloba costumbres humanas.txt 0.169918890033397
31. Juan del Encina -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\encina completo.txt 0.1718523856132721
32. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\lucenalibrocarto.txt 0.18333138813187067
33. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\repamorespreambuloajedrez.txt 0.18460107220447985
34. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\vita beata.txt 0.19824688469366025
35. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Ramirez Lucena a Jorge Manrique.txt 0.20846280527813854

²⁴ The Java Graphical Authorship Attribution Program

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36. Hernando del Castillo -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\hernando de castillo prologo.txt 0.21504128911212828
 37. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\RamirezLucena a Zapata.txt 0.21792654485114493
 38. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Ramirez Lucena exhortatoria.txt 0.2179979548168487
 39. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\ramirezlucena sermon.txt 0.2383867194661078
 40. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Lucena poema pp69-70.txt 0.2519584457269485
 41. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\RamirezLucena a galardones.txt 0.254715657190145

damianolibro1.txt D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\damianolibro1.txt

Canoniziers:

Normalize Whitespace

EventDrivers:

Character NGrams n : 2

EventCullers:

Most Common Events numevents : 50

Analysis:

Nearest Neighbor Driver with metric Cosine Distance

1. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\ramirezlucena1503.txt 0.09563635805296311
2. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\repamores cartas principio lucena.txt 0.11973691497203609
3. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\lucenaintroduccionajedrez.txt 0.12167393539548965
4. Alonso de Cardona -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\alonsodecardona lleva todo.txt 0.12946739195904633
5. Fernando de Rojas -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\fernando de rojas test2.txt 0.13601749463876855
6. Diego de San Pedro -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\carceldeamor.txt 0.13690776656595527
7. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\celestina monologos calisto.txt 0.1428961553310525
8. Diego de San Pedro -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\arnalte obra completa.txt 0.14614370088038442
9. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\repamorespreambulo.txt 0.1518143465430103
10. Francisco de Villaloba -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\villalobosglosa.txt 0.1530781756589199
11. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\repeticionamores.txt 0.15321265270278495
12. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Lucena pp 15-37.txt 0.15384899580305322
13. Fernando de Rojas -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\fernando de rojas3.txt 0.1587789620250949
14. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\lucena preambulo.txt 0.15916692927357612
15. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\vitabeata prologo.txt 0.16113379752942558
16. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Lucena pp37-59.txt 0.16416149720387452
17. Alonso de Proaza -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\alonsodeproaza4.txt 0.16501151646372691
18. Fernando de Rojas -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\fernando de rojas1 testamento notario.txt 0.16570416097696428
19. Juan de Flores -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\grimalteobra.txt 0.16690795793331925
20. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Lucena pp59-66.txt 0.1694823858311899
21. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\lucenalibrocarta.txt 0.17001628481044495
22. Juan del Encina -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\encina al principe.txt 0.17604470554288576
23. Francisco de Villaloba -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\villaloboscintas.txt 0.17608889200663613
24. Alonso de Proaza -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\proaza Toledo1500.txt 0.18124577932644925
25. Francisco de Villaloba -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\villaloba costumbres humanas.txt 0.18193712665237427
26. Alonso de Proaza -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\proaza acrostico.txt 0.18360762314495394
27. Juan de Flores -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\griselobra.txt 0.18613689277027867
28. Juan del Encina -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\encina completo.txt 0.1868998287972028
29. Juan del Encina -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\encina1521.txt 0.18746287336710443
30. Juan del Encina -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\encina eglogas antes 1509.txt 0.1883281382221087
31. Juan del Encina -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\encinacoplas1521.txt 0.18926770031528461

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SALES:

<http://www.lulu.com/spotlight/moriscoricote>

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32. Alonso de Proaza -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\proaza Valencia1514.txt 0.18961931975303192
33. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\vita beata.txt 0.202955008241124
34. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\repamorespreambuloaajedrez.txt 0.2149940308335505
35. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\RamirezLucena a Zapata.txt 0.22300810661047965
36. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Ramirez Lucena exhortatoria.txt 0.22304456350584512
37. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Ramirez Lucena a Jorge Manrique.txt 0.22585976943767838
38. Hernando del Castillo -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\hernando de castillo prologo.txt 0.23396919439382335
39. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\ramirezlucena sermon.txt 0.2515852365340855
40. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Lucena poema pp69-70.txt 0.25392325863242493
41. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\RamirezLucena a galardones.txt 0.27071125942978924

JGAAP shows us that Francesch Vicent's writing style is equal to Lucena's. So the letter Lucena wrote to the king in 1503, the principal letters at the beginning of the book *Repetición de amores*, and the introduction of Lucena in his chess book *Arte de Ajedrez* have the same writing style as Francesch Vicent's:

1. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\ramirezlucena1503.txt 0.0968743414097899
2. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\repamores cartas principio lucena.txt 0.10183801264860648
3. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\lucenaintroduccionajedrez.txt 0.11894348904134322

Consequently, Damiano wrote a chess book in Rome in 1512 that appears to be a pseudonym for Francesch Vicent and Francesh Vicent is Lucena, according to JGAAP. This chess book is followed by the editions of Damiano in Rome in 1518, 1524 and 1535. Antonio Blado printed the chess book of Damiano in 1524 and Blado was also involved in the tricky printing of *La Celestina* in 1520, which bears the year 1502 and was destined for Antonio de Salamanca who was an editor in Rome.

Two Spanish inventions in the XV – century

SALES:

<http://www.lulu.com/spotlight/moriscoricote>

Academia de Estudios Humanísticos de Blanca, 2016, N° 5, pp. 1-18

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An old chess book of Lucena (1497) in the Pierpont Morgan Library

The old Spanish chess books from the 15th century continue to be of interest for chess historians²⁵. Chess scholars found an old chess book of Lucena in the Pierpont Morgan Library in New York²⁶.

It was a surprise to see handwritten notes at the end of many problems in this book, because they are written in Valencian by a chess player at the end of the 15th century or at most in the early 16th century. Thanks to this work it was possible to obtain sufficient handwritten text for JGAAP – Character Ngrams n:2 that gives the following result:

vicent2015-2 Lucena New York.txt D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\vicent2015-2 Lucena New York.txt

Canonicizers:

Normalize Whitespace

EventDrivers:

Character NGrams n : 2

EventCullers:

Most Common Events numevents : 50

Analysis:

Nearest Neighbor Driver with metric Cosine Distance

1. Fernando de Rojas -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\fernando de rojas3.txt 0.058787592912751485
2. Fernando de Rojas -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\fernando de rojas1 testamento notario.txt 0.06056951779532915
3. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\ramirezlucena1503.txt 0.06968191537068291
4. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\lucenaintroduccionajedrez.txt 0.07124821542107584
5. Diego de San Pedro -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\carceldeamor.txt 0.0734783145855531
6. Francisco de Villaloba -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\villalobosglosa.txt 0.07461019789054169
7. Alonso de Cardona -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\alonsodecardona lleva todo.txt 0.0774682671246335
8. Fernando de Rojas -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\fernando de rojas test2.txt 0.07794189473367774
9. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Lucena pp59-66.txt 0.07998799331276862
10. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\repeticionamores.txt 0.08063604680624159
11. Juan del Encina -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\encina al principe.txt 0.08107656944388553
12. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\repamorespreambulo.txt 0.08245957472029708
13. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Lucena pp 15-37.txt 0.08435900390665096
14. Francisco de Villaloba -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\villaloba costumbres humanas.txt 0.08446652557607093
15. Diego de San Pedro -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\arnalte obra completa.txt 0.08670077503893914
16. Juan del Encina -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\encina completo.txt 0.08737861946781011
17. Francisco de Villaloba -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\villaloboscintas.txt 0.08840586327293698
18. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Lucena pp37-59.txt 0.08945700533464707

²⁵ **D'ELIA, Diego** (2006) Sulla più testimonianza di un testo scacchistico a stampa: le bozze di stampa dell'incunabolo "Arte de Axeddrez" di Luis Ramírez de Lucena". *Culture del testo del documento*, 19, pp. 81-98

²⁶ **GARZÓN ROGER, José Antonio** (2014) La búsqueda del Santo Grial del Ajedrez. Versión provisional para web. In: Pasiones bibliográficas. Trabajos conmemorativos del XX Aniversario de la Societat Bibliogràfica Valenciana Jerònima Galés, pp. 1-19

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19. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\repamores cartas principio lucena.txt 0.09046018792004196
20. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\celestina monologos calisto.txt 0.09176779358303999
21. Alonso de Proaza -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\proaza Toledo1500.txt 0.09316406504762498
22. Juan de Flores -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\grimalteobra.txt 0.09613076813374954
23. Juan de Flores -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\griselobra.txt 0.09655846762210019
24. Alonso de Proaza -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\proaza Valencia1514.txt 0.09804859660983956
25. Alonso de Proaza -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\proaza acrostico.txt 0.09990332324012996
26. Alonso de Proaza -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\alonsodeproaza4.txt 0.10033289466700146
27. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\vitabeata prologo.txt 0.10072261665351934
28. Juan del Encina -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\encina eglogas antes 1509.txt 0.1027098359929507
29. Juan del Encina -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\encinacoplas1521.txt 0.10597618099814532
30. Juan del Encina -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\encina1521.txt 0.10723423850949698
31. Hernando del Castillo -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\hernando de castillo prologo.txt 0.1181988771621032
32. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\vita beata.txt 0.11876963138799146
33. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\lucenalibrocarto.txt 0.12241972302607651
34. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Ramirez Lucena exhortatoria.txt 0.12554659483995134
35. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\RamirezLucena a Zapata.txt 0.12571266433627082
36. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Ramirez Lucena a Jorge Manrique.txt 0.12606093336881818
37. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\lucena preambulo.txt 0.12696575844583857
38. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\ramirezlucena sermon.txt 0.13646874439910728
39. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\RamirezLucena a galardones.txt 0.15897684732924522
40. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Lucena poema pp69-70.txt 0.17802739499090003
41. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\repamorespreambuloajedrez.txt 0.1798987365612903

The text resulted to be by Fernando de Rojas.

Fernando de Rojas Testamento	Fernando de Rojas Testamento	Diego de San Pedro Foreword Carcel de amor	Lucena Letter of 1503 to King Ferdinand	Lucena Introduction Chess book 1497
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However, so far we know that Fernando de Rojas did not speak Valencian, thus the handwritten notes can be Lucena's. This may be fortified by another test of JGAAP, this time with Character NGrams n:4?

Lucena Letters Repeticion de amores	Lucena Letter of 1503 to King Ferdinand	Diego de San Pedro Carcel de amor	Diego de San Pedro Foreword Carcel de amor	Juan del Encina Letter to Prince
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vicent2015-2 Lucena New York.txt D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\vicent2015-2 Lucena New York.txt
Canonicizers:

Normalize Whitespace

EventDrivers:

Character NGrams n : 4

EventCullers:

Most Common Events numevents : 50

Analysis:

Nearest Neighbor Driver with metric Cosine Distance

1. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\repamores cartas principio lucena.txt 0.19567391828762992
2. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\ramirezlucena1503.txt 0.19633332941690862
3. Diego de San Pedro -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\carceldeamor.txt 0.2026411118092889
4. Juan del Encina -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\encina al principe.txt 0.2121599303174838
5. Juan de Flores -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\griselobra.txt 0.21278514337527066
6. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\repcionamores.txt 0.21743690266765403
7. Juan del Encina -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\encina completo.txt 0.2181110075695395
8. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Lucena pp37-59.txt 0.21818008847178405
9. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\celestina monologos calisto.txt 0.22025898530409793
10. Diego de San Pedro -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\arnalte obra completa.txt 0.22097793202099048
11. Francisco de Villaloba -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\vallalobosglosa.txt 0.2232429783939417
12. Juan del Encina -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\encina eglogas antes 1509.txt 0.22496185265312962
13. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\repamorespreambulo.txt 0.2255915058305772
14. Francisco de Villaloba -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\vallaloba costumbres humanas.txt 0.23175301934276837
15. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\lucenaintroduccionajedrez.txt 0.23610744048062493
16. Hernando del Castillo -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\hernando de castillo prologo.txt 0.2366121603421193
17. Alonso de Cardona -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\alonsodecardona lleva todo.txt 0.23714371674435586
18. Juan de Flores -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\grimalteobra.txt 0.2432070135863451
19. Juan del Encina -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\encinacoplas1521.txt 0.24426123807450728
20. Francisco de Villaloba -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\vallaloboscintas.txt 0.24595844717890902
21. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Lucena pp59-66.txt 0.24717146284503122
22. Alonso de Proaza -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\alonsodeproaza4.txt 0.24833381365908302
23. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Lucena pp 15-37.txt 0.25162719484223406
24. Juan del Encina -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\encina1521.txt 0.2550982612528806
25. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\vita beata.txt 0.2620745825886517
26. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\vitateata prologo.txt 0.2643962911021195
27. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Ramirez Lucena exhortatoria.txt 0.26520063254159654
28. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\RamirezLucena a Zapata.txt 0.26573941693395664
29. Fernando de Rojas -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\fernando de rojas3.txt 0.26797497929765224
30. Fernando de Rojas -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\fernando de rojas1 testamento notario.txt 0.27153319890772853
31. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\lucena preambulo.txt 0.27200142755112233
32. Alonso de Proaza -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\proaza Valencia1514.txt 0.27491825283913485
33. Alonso de Proaza -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\proaza Toledo1500.txt 0.2878690887325501

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34. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Ramirez Lucena a Jorge Manrique.txt 0.294346492792956
35. Alonso de Proaza -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\proaza acrostico.txt 0.29768991086287055
36. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\ramirezlucena sermon.txt 0.3066031894110035
37. Fernando de Rojas -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\fernando de rojas test2.txt 0.32381172412261827
38. Juan Ramirez de Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\RamirezLucena a galardones.txt 0.34591246677578324
39. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\lucenalibrocerto.txt 0.4359010329489166
40. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\Lucena poema pp69-70.txt 0.5029625943841205
41. Lucena -D:\Programas text analysis\Signatura\repamorespreambuloajedrez.txt 0.8092595790361955

CONCLUSION

We observe from all these data that the pseudonym Lucena, son of the Ambassador Juan Ramirez de Lucena, in reality could be nobody else than Francesch Vicent. Furthermore, Francesch Vicent established himself at first in Ferrara as chess master of Lucrecia Borgia and after some time started working in Rome near the Papal Court. He was not willing to use his real name in books and social life. For that reason we see nicknames in the chess books, while he worked in Rome under a pseudonym or nickname.